

Development of Psyllium-Potato Starch film: A Biodegradable shield for pure Diclofenac sodium against photodegradation

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ABSTRACT:

The research focused on analysing the UV barrier properties of psyllium biopolymeric composite films to develop novel, innovative primary packaging systems for light-sensitive drug substances. The psyllium and potato starch films were fabricated using the solvent casting method. The maximum absorbance of pure diclofenac sodium was observed at 276 nm, with a regression coefficient of 0.9989. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) results indicated no physical interaction between the drug and the excipients. Pure diclofenac sodium was encapsulated in both psyllium-starch and plain starch films. The percent transmittance of the psyllium biopolymeric composite films at 240 nm was approximately 39.5 %, indicating a higher degree of opacity, which correlates with lower transmittance, compared to the starch film without psyllium, which showed 82%. After 10 minutes of UV exposure, the percent protection of pure diclofenac sodium was increased by 86.03 % when using the psyllium-starch film, compared to the plain starch film, which provided only 62.31 % of UV protection.

KEYWORDS: Photodegradation, psyllium bio-polymeric composite films, diclofenac sodium, UV protection.

1. Introduction

It is well known that the light can change the properties of different materials and products. In the field of pharmacy, photostability has played an important role meanwhile the number of drugs found to be photo-chemically unstable is steadily increasing. The European pharmacopeia prescribes light protection for more than 250 medical drugs and adjuvants. It is necessary to understand the nature and extent of photodegradation: the mechanism of the light-induced degradation reaction; and the wavelength causing the instability. To reduce the potential problems raised by photo unstable drugs it is necessary to develop a strategy to minimize the photodegradation of the light sensitive drugs.

Depending on the nature of the drug product it is susceptible to light -induced degradation. It can be identified early in the initial stages of analytical method development. A commonly experienced problem during this stage relates to the degree of freedom in the purity of the compound, degree of knowledge regarding the degradation of products, validation master plan and availability of the new chemical entity (NCE) [1].

While the photochemical and photobiological properties of a number of class of drugs (such as antimalarials, phenothiazines, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicines, etc.) have been thoroughly studied, less is known about other bioactive substances [2].

Diclofenac, a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug used for the treatment arthritis, muscle cramps. It has been reported to be not stable and undergo photodegradation processes. Stability studies of this compound showed several potential impurities. The main impurity, 1-(2,6-dichlorophenyl) indolin-2-one, may occur in pharmaceutical formulations after long-term storage. This research

aims to investigate how diclofenac breaks down when exposed to light. The light sensitivity of drug substances requires the use of an effective packaging system to protect them from photochemical damage. Psyllium biopolymeric composite film can improve the UV barrier properties of starch with psyllium mucilage, making them especially valuable for primary packing systems for light-sensitive drug substances.

The psyllium hydrocolloid found in psyllium seeds is a highly branched polysaccharide, where xylopyranose residues constitute the main chain. In contrast, the side chains are made up of arabinofuranosyl and xylopyranosyl units [3].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Psyllium seeds was brought from a supplier ponmani and co., diclofenac sodium was purchased from Yarrow chem products, Mumbai. Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose, glycerol, propylene glycol and starch were purchased from Loba chemie pvt Ltd.

2.2. METHODOLOGY

Extraction of mucilage from psyllium

6gm of seeds were soaked in 120 ml distilled water. The mixture was kept for 24 h, then it was boiled at 60 °C for 20min. the obtained mucilage was filtered to remove the residue.

Preparation of psyllium biopolymeric composite film

Three grams of Psyllium seeds were soaked in 60 ml of distilled water for 24 h and then boiled for 30 min. 2 g of potato starch in 20 ml of distilled water was boiled separately and 4 g of HPMC in 40 ml of water was added to the above mucilage. The above mixtures were stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 30 min at 600 rpm. 4 ml of glycerin was added to the above mixture with continuous stirring. The mold was lubricated with glycerin. The mixture was casted on cleaned petri dish for appropriate thickness. The film was dried in an oven for 1 h at 70 °C [3,4].

Determination of λ_{max} of Diclofenac sodium: The maximum absorbance of diclofenac sodium was studied and found to be 276 nm.

Preparation of standard solution

100 mg of diclofenac sodium was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10 ml standard flask. It was then dissolved in methanol and the volume was made up to the marking with methanol.

Construction of calibration curve for diclofenac sodium

The UV-Vis spectrophotometric method was used to analyse diclofenac sodium. The series of dilution containing 10,20,30,40 and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was made with methanol. The absorbance of the drug was measured at 276 nm [5,7].

Drug interaction studies using ATR FT-IR

In order to identify the functional groups and interactions of diclofenac sodium with excipients were subjected to ATR FT-IR spectroscopic analysis. The obtained spectrum of the drug was compared with the drug excipient physical mixtures [6].

UV-VIS barrier properties (opacity and light transmittance)

The light transmission and transparency of the film were evaluated in film dimensions of $10 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ in dimension. The specimens were placed in the aperture of a double beam UV-vis spectroscopy and transmittance was measured in the range of 200-800 nm.

The transparency of the O_{240} film was calculated from

$$O_{240} = \log T_{240}/e$$

Where O_{240} is transparency (AU/mm), T_{240} is transmittance at a wavelength of 240 nm and e is the thickness of the film [4,9,10].

3. Photodegradation test according to the ICH guidelines (Laminar air flow-Techinco LV-42)

Three Petri dishes was washed thoroughly in distilled water followed by acetone. The pure diclofenac sodium alone, diclofenac sodium wrapped with plain starch film and psyllium composite film. The samples were exposed to UV chamber for 10 min. 10 mg of drug was diluted in 10 ml methanol and further diluted to obtain

10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The samples were analysed to determine the percentage protection of drug[8,11].

Fig.1 Photo-degradation test conducted for samples in UV chamber.

4. Percentage protection after exposure of pure diclofenac sodium packed in films

The amount of the diclofenac sodium protected in with and without wrapping in the film was identified by exposing all the samples in UV chamber at 10 min. The sample was retrieved and diluted in ethanol. The absorbance was noted and the percentage protection was determined by the transmittance formula[4,12,13].

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

Standard Calibration Curve of Diclofenac Sodium

The maximum absorbance of diclofenac sodium was studied and found to be 276 nm.

Table.1 Calibration data of diclofenac sodium

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (276 nm)
0	0
10	0.328
20	0.745
30	1.078

40	1.383
50	1.677

Fig.2 Calibration curve of diclofenac sodium

Drug interaction studies using ATR FT-IR meth

In order to identify the functional groups and interactions of diclofenac sodium with excipients were subjected to ATR FT-IR spectroscopic analysis. The obtained spectrum of the drug was compared with the drug excipient physical mixtures. There are no interaction identified between pure diclofenac sodium and excipients.

Fig.3 FT-IR spectrum of pure Diclofenac sodium

Table.2 spectral bands of functional groups present in Diclofenac sodium

Functional group	Wave number cm^{-1}
N-H stretch	2922 cm^{-1}
C-Cl stretch	742 cm^{-1}
C=O stretch	1544 cm^{-1}
C=C stretch	1446 cm^{-1}
C-H stretch	2848 cm^{-1}

Fig.4 FT-IR spectrum of Diclofenac sodium + psyllium powder

Wavenumber [cm^{-1}]**Fig.5 FT-IR spectrum of Diclofenac sodium+ starch****Opacity and light transmittance test**

The opacity and the light transmittance were determined by the exposure of the diclofenac sodium wrapped separately in both starch film and psyllium composite film. As opacity is inversely proportional to transmittance, the opacity of psyllium composite film is higher than starch hence it shows lower transmittance.

Table.3 opacity and light transmittance test of psyllium composite film and plain starch film

Sample	T_{240} (%)	Opacity (AU/mm)
Starch/HPMC	82	3.18
Psyllium extract/starch/HPMC	39.5	7.98

Percentage protection after exposure of pure diclofenac sodium packed in films

The opacity and the light transmittance were determined by the exposure of the diclofenac sodium wrapped separately in both starch film and psyllium composite film as the diclofenac sodium wrapped with psyllium composite shows more protection than the drug wrapped with plain starch film. The results are given in the Table.8.

Table.4 Percentage protection after exposure of pure diclofenac sodium packed in films.

Samples	Percentage protection
Pure diclofenac sodium	40.24
Diclofenac sodium in plain starch film	62.31
Diclofenac sodium in psyllium polymeric composite	86.03

Fig.6 Percentage protection of diclofenac sodium in UV chamber at 10 min

SUMMARY

- The wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{\max}) of diclofenac sodium was found to be at 276 nm. The correlation coefficient (r^2) was found to be 0.9989, and the slope value was found to be 0.0345.
- The spectrum of diclofenac sodium was compared with excipients and there were no significant interactions between drug and the excipients.
- Psyllium seed mucilage with potato starch films were prepared using the solvent casting method.
- The transmittance and opacity values at 240 nm for the prepared films were collected from a UV-visible spectrophotometer, as shown in Table 4. Adding psyllium led to a significant decrease in UV transmittance (T_{240}), while opacity values increased.
- Films with psyllium showed lower percent transmittance compared to potato starch films, suggesting that psyllium-potato starch films could have good barrier properties against UV light.
- The percent protection after exposing the pure diclofenac sodium in UV light in a petri dish directly, after packing it in starch film and psyllium

with starch film for about 10 min, was found to be 40.24, 62.31, and 86.03 %, respectively.

Conclusion

- In the present study, psyllium with potato starch films were fabricated using the solvent casting method. They showed opacity at 240 nm that was 2.5 times higher than in the potato starch films alone. The lower transmittance suggests an effective improvement in barrier properties against UV light
- The amount of drug remaining in the psyllium polymeric composite film improved by 86.03 % compared to plain starch film.

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